

Chapter 00 | International topics

DCA_ Strategies and Design Teaching:

Process and Product of Design: Experimental Studio Design on Techniques of Fashion and Architecture

Mahwish Ghulam Rasool, Department of Interior design, Indus Valley School of Art and Architecture, Karachi, Pakistan

Abstract

Design education and practice is constantly changing and evolving around the world. The process of training future designers is quite dynamic as it involves various theoretical and pragmatic approaches but the most evident and similar practice around the world is the prominence of studio teaching which act as a prime medium of instruction. It involves various intensive cognitive and physical activities which aim for conceptualization of various design solution.

Design studio act as an incubator space which needs constant fuel of creativity to keep the thinking process of students active, therefore it needs creative methodologies to keep the process interactive and imaginative. The methodology of conventional studio design has drastically changed in past 10 years as its not only the place of learning the process of design but also an experimental lab in which one can invent the possible design techniques from various disciplines. It's also changing its dynamics from disciplinary to interdisciplinary practices which involves the study, knowledge and techniques from various related professions.

Similar is the case with Architecture and Fashion education that there techniques, creation of forms, surface treatments, concept of skins and the process to create surfaces are similar in many ways. Such as fashion designers have taken inspiration from buildings and Architects are inspired by fashion designers for new ideas to achieve more fluid and complex forms. As rightly said by Hani Rashid that "Structure Pattern for space is the same way you structure pattern for the body". These manipulations and cross techniques allows both fields to reach higher level of creativity and sophistication.

The paper is based on similar idea of an experimental studio methodology which takes inspirations and techniques from fashion and architecture to create surfaces and forms. The objective of this experimental studio exercise is to enhance the conceptual and technical skill of the student and enhances creative inquiry and imagination. The paper is structured in two parts the first part will explore the potentials of fashion and architecture in theory and practice by analyzing the work of different architects and designers like Peter Eisenman, Calvin Klein, Zaha Hadid, Hussain Chahayan, Herzog and De Meuron, Yoshiki Hishinuma etc.

The second part will briefly talk about the studio methodology, its conception, the process of design and the final product or installation created in the studio exercise. The last part will further talk about the possibilities of future models in Design studio teaching both manual and virtual.

Research Aim:

The aim of this research is to connect theories of fashion and architecture into a studio module to learn from experimentation of two parallel fields, there similarities and techniques.

To introduce interdisciplinary approach of learning in design studio to further promote creative and cognitive skills of students.

Research questions:

Discipline specific design methodology vs interdisciplinary design methodology?

How the techniques can be learned parallel in design studio?

How the parallel techniques will help students to create spaces which are more cohesive, creative and imaginative?

Keywords

Design education, Architecture, interior design, fashion, form, surfaces, interdisciplinary.

1. Introduction

In design pedagogy studio teaching is the fundamental core of design curriculum. It's the main model of learning which includes the knowledge of design techniques, skills, crafts, ideas development, imaginative and cognitive skills etc. It's a complex medium of learning where ideas are generated, represented and reviewed (Mike, 2015).

The early structure of design education dates back to classical times in which young apprentice served under the mastery of an accompanied Master/architect. Where a master designer, craftsman shared his knowledge, wisdom and skills with his apprentice. Many Great architects - designers from classical to modern masters went through a similar approach of learning.

The early roots of formal design education, traced back to the nineteenth century ateliers of the École des Beaux Arts located in Paris. In École des Beaux-Arts, the students were offered theory courses and ateliers (Amir, 2001). On various subjects the studios (ateliers) brought a new approach to the architectural design education which can be described as "learning by doing" (Schön, 1987). Since then, the **studio teaching** has been the core of the design education system.

Similar is the case with Interior Design education, in most institutions, its structured around two main ideas—building knowledge in a variety of related subjects and the development of a range of visual and tactile representation skills. Components of knowledge include the history, theory and methodology of design, and the skills include sketching, rendering, drawings, model making, computer visualization, and various other visual communication skills (Lauren, Prasad, 2014). These educational goals are typically achieved through lecture courses and project-based learning studios. Usually the courses are structure towards discipline specific knowledge.

In the last 20 years due to the cross overs in many design fields, Interdisciplinary education is getting popular in many design curriculums. In design education, interdisciplinary collaborations is a natural consequence of varying and developing knowledge areas and aims to Provide students with multi-purpose way of thinking(Ekran,2013).

This approach encourages students to improve their skills, abilities self-confidence and provide more effective communication between the different disciplines.

(Masters, Baker end Jodon 2012). It is defined as one of the most creative process to indulge critical thinking of cross disciplines (Ekran, 2013).

Studio methodology is based on two main components, how to generate ideas and how to represent them into realistic drawing and visual mediums (Soliman, 2017) Creation of ideas and representations of ideas both have equal importance in design education. It was observed that in a spatial design second year interior design studio, students generate great ideas but they face hindrance in visual representation of Ideas effectively.

For countering various such problems the studio tutors planned to introduce an experimental workshop in the skill based VisCom studio on learning techniques of form, skin and surface based on parallel practices of Architecture, Fashion and Space.

This decade brings many technological and complex challenges, design problems are even more complex in nature and it's not entirely discipline specific. Similar is the case with interior design education due to its multifaceted nature which involves approaches from various design fields. To comprehend the challenges of human environment and its complex nature interdisciplinary teaching is the new pedagogical approach to interior design education.

The idea of introducing interdisciplinary approach of teaching in Interior design degree program IVS, it was discussed in the course reviews meetings about the possibilities of education modules and for a start the idea was to introduce one experimental workshop to introduce parallel techniques of forms exploration by linking to the field of architectonic form and fashion form. The experiment workshop was planned as a non-conventional studio module both in terms of communication techniques and the methodology of techniques.

The paper will further discuss the parallel practices, influences, theories and techniques which are similar in both the profession and how they can be learned parallel in a VisCom studio module to facilitate student learning in terms of crafting, model making and techniques (visual presentation) so that they can express their ideas more creative and cohesive.

2. Parallel Techniques of Fashion and Architecture in Studio, Practice and Research

Architecture and fashion practice both express ideas of personal, social and cultural identity, reflecting the concerns of the user and the ambition of the age. Their relationship is a symbiotic one, throughout history clothing and buildings have echoed each other in form and appearance. This seems only natural as they share the primary function of providing shelter and protection for the body and also they create space and volume out of flat, two-dimensional materials. While they have much in common, they are also intrinsically different. Both address the human scale, but the proportions, sizes and shapes differ enormously. And while fashion is, by its very nature, ephemeral or 'of the moment', architecture traditionally has a more solid, monumental and permanent presence. (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

Architecture and fashion **education** also have vast similarities both in terms of learning about the design process and also in its application. It includes ideas about creation of forms, skin and structure to surface creating techniques like pleating, folding, adding volume, construction of forms etc. There pedagogical approaches also revolves mainly around studio teaching. Many modernist (Henry Van de Velde, Josef Holfman, Frank Lord Wright and Adolf loos designed clothes and wrote about fashion.(Leila, 2000, pg.472).

In Architecture history, Architects were concerned directly with dress, either as an effort to reform modern appearances or as part of the scenography of interiors. Modernist associate this cross learning or parallel with Arts and Crafts movement, Art Nouveau and Vieneses secession (Leila, 2000, pg.473). After the publication of books such as Elizabeth Wilson "Adorned in Dreams (1985) accentuated issues that made fashion relevant for architecture historians and it's link to mass communication, industrial design and urban spectacle. But not until the publication of Architecture in Fashion by Deborah Fausch 1994 after that fashion was granted an explanatory role in relation to modern architects. (Leila, 2000, pg.473)

Exhibition named **fertile grounds the 1980s** act as a starting point of significant cultural shifts in practice of both architecture and fashion. 1980s was a period of great cultural change, diversity, energy and inquiry. It started with the city of London then went to the major fashion cities of the world like New York, Paris, and Tokyo. Boundaries between the disciplines seemed to merge as creative cultures came together in a dialogue that promoted a rich exchange of ideas and possibilities. This period provided fertile ground for a generation of architects and designers in their formative years. In 1980 the way architecture and fashion was presented in the media changed radically from being specialists or rather

discipline specific to cross cultural, architecture and visual discourse was integrated into a broader view of visual and culture and style. (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

In 1982 blueprint was launched in London it was among the first magazines to cross the boundaries between fashion and architecture and its broad remit included architecture, interiors, fashion, furniture and industrial design. In 1982 the architect Bernard Tschumi won the international competition to design Parc De La Viltte in Paris. His project and the resulting collaborations between Architect Eisenman and philosopher Jacques Derida included ideas of **deconstruction in architecture**. In 1988 the seminal exhibition "Deconstructivist architecture "opened at the MOMA modern Art Museums New York. (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

In 1982, the museum at the MIT mounted an exhibition called "Intimate architecture Contemporary clothing design ". Curated by Susan Sidlauskas, It examined the formal aspects of the works of eight fashion designers including Yeohlee Teng from an architecture point of view. This influential exhibition was the first public presentation of fashion that analyzed the architecture aspects of contemporary clothing designs and made more formal connections between the two practices. In 1990 saw the introduction of sophisticated computer aided design program, which enabled architects to create increasingly complex surfaces and unusual forms. Complex forms in both fashion and architecture or interior spaces were came into realization from paper to reality in the later 90s.The works of Margiela, Hussain Chahayan, Viktor and Rolf, Zaha Hadid, Herzog De Meuron expresses true amalgamation of the parallel practices (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

The current interest of parallels and similarities in the field happened in the late 90s follow by about a decade of scholarly interest in other disciplines. Which itself was prompted by a number of methodological shifts. For most of this century, anthropology, sociology, and costume institutes have emphasized comparative and developmental taxonomies of dress, or the social dramaturgy of nonverbal communication through clothes. (Leila, 2000, pg.473)

Figure 1. Fashion and fabrication, (Leila W., 2000. pp.474 (figure1. Goffried Semper, 1860)

In recent years, the current interest of parallels between fashion and architecture have become even more intriguing. As advances in materials technology and computer software have pushed the frontiers of each discipline, buildings have become more fluid and garments more architectonic. Architects are adopting strategies more usually used in dressmaking, such as printing, pleating, folding, draping and weaving, while fashion designers are looking to architecture for ways to build or engineer garments which present new and provocative ideas about volume and structure, and in many cases also draw on the intellectual principles and concepts inherent in architecture. (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

In the creative exhibition by coco channel in 2011, where he expressed his view of the design of clothing line which takes inspiration from architecture to create the mood of a collection; he explained that without the set the clothes are merely garments, but the combination of clothing and the surrounding space makes a connection that conveys a mood and a sense of completion (Palencia, 2014).

Figure2. Channel couture collection. (Lagerfeld, 2011-2012)

Throughout the 69 looks that were presented there were architectural references in the clothing, mostly in the construction of the garments and in the overall silhouette; the elongated lines interrupted by precise and textured layering, the innovative volume of sleeves, skirts and jacket details and the placement of seams and embellishments were a constant reminder that this collection was inspired by the city which Coco Chanel herself adored. The images below exemplify the intersection of architecture and fashion, in this case linked to the city of Paris. (Palencia, 2014).

Figure 3. Channel couture collection. (Lagerfeld, 2011-2012)

Furthermore, Brooke Hodge, 2008 explains that the intersection of fashion and architecture originates in the similarities in the creative process of both practices. Both fashion designers and architects begin with taking an idea, analyzing its practical requirements, making sketches and developing study models that will later be transformed into three-Dimensional structures that mark the first steps of the creation of products in each practice. While fashion designers have the luxury of being able to work directly on the body in early stages of the creative process because of the scale of what is being built, architects are required to use a series of scale models to communicate design as they rarely build a full-scale mock-up of what is being created. Many Notations and instructions are to be made on each project, and these standard guidelines can be found both in architectural drawings and in dressmaker's patterns.

The paper will review the basic form and surface manipulation techniques of fashion and architecture. The most common cross overs in the work of the designers and architects are seen in the following.

3. Cross overs in forms, Structure skin and Surface

3.1 Geometry:

The use of geometry to generate form is a strategy shared by both architects and fashion designers. Simple forms such as circles, squares and eclipses as well as more complex forms such as the torus and the Mobius strip are used in both the disciplines. These techniques are also known as tectonic strategies, the most commonly used tectonic strategies are folding, pleating, wrapping and weaving. They affect the structure, column and proportion of the design both in a built form or a garment (Palencia, 2014). In Architecture, geometry is often used to create complex interior spaces, they shape the overall physical form of the space whereas in Fashion Design once a garment is draped on a body, its shape is transformed and the geometry that is generated often became invisible (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley, 2008 skin n bones).

Figure 4. Max Reinhardt Haus building in Berlin. (Eisenman architects, 2015). Mobius Dress. (J. Meejin Yoon's, 2005)

Two designers J. Meejin Yoon and Eisenman Architects successfully challenge the forms of geometry. J. Meejin Yoon's Mobius Dress of 2005 (Fig.4) resembles the complexity of geometry within a design. Many of Yoon's designs lead onto larger scale projects as her studio also deals with architecture and installations. The Mobius Dress explores the form and complexity of the Mobius strip; a never ending, "one-sided, one-edged" loop with

"no fixed orientation." The design forms three connected loops around the body, zips feature on the cut line holding the dress together enclosing the figure in a "stiff A-line shape" then the unzipped interlocking felt loops fall to the floor (Podesta, 2013).

When a model is dressed the true complication of the geometry holds its structure very similar to the Max Reinhardt Haus building in Berlin by Eisenman Architects (Fig.4) when designing the thirty-four story multi-purpose tower Eisenman indulged in the challenge of investigating the complex geometry of a building by altering orientation. The Mobius strip was a perfect starting point with two "complex prismatic" towers. Connected by a "twisting arch." The geometry of such a complex form such as the Mobius strip is a challenge to both architecture and fashion however when the challenge is taken both can succeed by producing reflective iconic designs (Podesta, 2013).

Figure 5. The Prada Store in Tokyo. (Herzog & de Meuron, 2003).Inside out 2way Dress. (Yoshiki Hishinuma, 2004)

3.2 Structural skin

The structural skin is a phrase known to both architects and fashion designers combining the 'skin and bones' of a concept, joining the body and façade to a solo surface. Yoshiki Hishinuma Inside Out 2way Dress featured in the Spring/Summer collection of 2004 (Fig.5) shows a unique way that a dress held together by "strips of opaque tape". Working as the bones of the design also works as the skin hiding parts of the body. This idea of taping pieces together transfers into the architecture of three designs; the Prada Store in Tokyo by Herzog & de Meuron, (Fig.5) Tod's Omotesando building in Tokyo by Toyo (Fig.6) and the Carbon Beach House in Los Angeles by Testa & Weiser (Fig.6). The three concepts undertook similar techniques if not the same as Hishinuma by binding the exterior shell and internal components creating a seamless pattern of the two the

new materials and technology created in the two fields cross paths on so many levels (Podesta, 2013).

Figure 6. Tod's Omotesando building. (Toyo, 2006).
The Carbon Beach House in Los Angeles. (Testa & Weiser)

3.3 Surface treatments

The metaphoric connection between fashion and architecture has been suggested since Vitruvius, and perhaps even earlier. German architect Gottfried Semper, also in the nineteenth century, argued that the origin of the architectural surface came from the textile, hide, or wattle, hung, or stretched between structural posts. Semper confirmed his system of architecture in a Caribbean cottage shown at the Great Exposition in London, which he wrote in *Der Stil* [Style in the Technical and Tectonic Art, or Practical Aesthetics], published in 1860–1863 (Semper et al. 2004). Adolf Loos, in his essay titled “The Principle of Cladding,” referred to “covering” as the basic and oldest architecture detail. He wrote, “This is the correct and logical path to be followed in architecture. It was in this sequence that mankind learned how to build. In the beginning was cladding...Originally it was made out of animal skins and textile products” (Loos 1982). (Jiangmei Wu, 2017)

Herzog and de Meuron, who have built their entire career on innovative and ingenious surface design, showed strong interests in the “aspect of artificial skin which becomes so much of an intimate part of people” (Herzog 1997). Office dA, another architecture firm, also showed a strong connection in their works to Semper's idea of architecture as cladding. For example, in Weston House, an adaptive reuse project, Office dA used new layers of cladding to cover and mask the original structure, as if they designed a “dress” to cover the body of building. For Office dA, the cladding “is understood and designed as a constitutive spatial elements as much as a vehicle to architectural and cultural signification” El-Khoury, 2001. (Jiangmei Wu, 2017). Similar example is Caixa forum Madrid in Barcelona where an external cladding is done as a part of surface treatment for the building.

4. Parallels in Vocabulary

Vocabulary derived from architecture has migrated to fashion so that garments can be described with words such as architectonic, constructed or sculptural, while other words from fashion have migrated to architecture and adapted to construction language, describing surfaces and materials as draping, wrapping, weaving, or folding. Moreover, it becomes evident that designers have been constantly influenced by the social and climatic conditions throughout history, and these elements have created a steady succession of interpretations in the form of fashion silhouettes or architectural forms, volumes and textures that are recreated and exposed in a contemporary context. This is most evident in the idea of clothing and structures as shelter. This connection dates back to the Ice Age, when people used animal skins to cover themselves and to fashion exterior walls for crude structures (Palencia, 2014).

4.1 Parallels in design process

The similar methods for innovating a design project in both fashion and architecture revolve around the concepts of intertwining, weaving, folding and pleating, amongst other terms, which have become part of the shared vocabulary that is applied to the different materials and techniques utilized in the construction of both garments and architectural works. In fashion this translates to words like “architectonic”, “sculptural” and “constructed”, which helps designers reference their work easily to a source of inspiration outside the realm of fashion.

5. Tectonic strategies

5.1 Techniques of folding

In Architecture, Fashion and Interior design, folding, both as a theoretical idea and as a means for form and surface generation, has inspired a new generation of architects and designers to create morphogenetic architectural volumes with continuous variations and interpolations that overlap gaps and avoid fracture (Lynn 2004). Morphological architectural structures are starting to make use of one of the main characteristics of folding design – the kinetic ability to deploy and collapse in three-dimensional space (Liapi 2002; Motro 2009). There are many more examples of origami-inspired foldable designs in interior objects and furniture, as well as collapsible interior walls and partitions.

Following are the examples of Yoshimura folding techniques shown in the fig 6 and fig 7. Folded paper model showing Yoshimura deployments resulting in a variety of topologies that can be applied to interior

surfaces. Similarly Flexible deployments of Yoshimura pattern in various Proximities to the body is shown in the figure 7.

Figure 6. Yoshimura pattern interior surfaces. (Jiangmei Wu, 2017)

Figure 7. Yoshimura pattern interior surfaces. (Jiangmei Wu, 2017)

6. Parallel Techniques in Material

For many years fashion designers and architects have been sharing the use of Materials and techniques, using them in similar ways but in contrasting scales. Materials such as steel; particularly noted in Gareth Pugh's designs in the film *Who Are You, Polly Maggoo* (Fig.8) where the harsh architectural quality of steel is used to design dresses. Techniques such as folding, wrapping and draping are used in both lines of design; clearly shown in the Walt Disney Concert Hall in Los Angeles by Frank Gehry (Fig.8), Wrapping the complicated structure in smooth, curvaceous, reflective sheets of steel as one wraps clothing around the compounds of the body in the style of a sarong. Not only are materials and techniques borrowed from one area to the other but also correlations made between a number of key factors such as; color, volume, texture, scale, geometry, and orientation (Podesta, 2013).

These links have become stronger as technologies have advanced allowing new forms and techniques to adapt to various uses for both building and clothing designs. The structure and surface of a design in both worlds do not have to be hidden, exposing the framework in fashion via seams, tubing, threading and stitching as it is using beams, columns, cables and bars in architecture. This helps to create the blurred connection between the figure

and the tools allowing communication and understanding without talking but developing the link between the decorative structures and the function. This exposure helps to develop and suggest ways in which buildings and clothing can be used to provide alternative functions (Podesta, 2013).

Figure 8. Walt Disney Concert Hall, (Frank Gehry, 1999-2003). *Who Are You, Polly Maggoo*. (Gareth Pugh, 1966).

Researching the many ways in which “both creative practices” interweave is extensive and noted in the developments of each discipline. The two areas are constantly learning from each other; architects look to fashion designers for new ideas to “achieve more fluid and complex forms out of hard materials” taking forms like pleating, wrapping and draping. Whilst fashion designers are exploring engineering techniques to create “architectonic garments using fabrics.” This “cross-contamination” of methods and design development in software and technology allows both practices to reach higher levels of sophistication. (Broke; Patricia; Mark and Wigley. 2008 skin n bones).

7. Experimental workshop methodology:

The VisCom studio in the second year interior design department teaches the core principles, techniques, and presentations for studio exercises. This minor studio module runs parallel to the main design studio to facilitate student presentation skills.

Students performance pattern was observed that even after a vigorous foundation year training in IVS. Students in interior design have issues in expressing their ideas by representation mediums. It was observed that in a design studio students generate great ideas but they face a general stuck that how to represent their Ideas, for countering various such problems the studio tutors planned to introduce an experimental workshop in the beginning of the 3rd semester with an objective to teach techniques of form, skin and surface, based on the theoretical principles of fashion, space and architecture.

Workshop had three clearly defined objectives:

1. To teach skills in form development, structural skin and surface manipulation
2. To teach the design and imaginative process
3. To teach surface form and skin concepts in interior architecture

The main objective is the introduction of complex set of techniques in representation of ideas through form understanding and model making. The idea was to teach them skills and tools for design application. The workshop was design for a week and students were divided in groups. The workshop was followed by introduction of fashion techniques by the fashion department in-house tutors and lectures of fashion and architecture parallel practices by the interior design tutor.

The **first day** of the workshop covered the theoretical premise of the exercise. Concept of form and shelter in both the practices were discussed, followed by crafting techniques to create surfaces. For designers the same techniques are used for crafting shelter for the body and for interior architects the same philosophy is crafting interior spaces for human use and comfort.

The **second day** of the workshop taught the basic origami techniques and introduction of tectonic strategies of form like folding, wrapping, pleating, tucking etc., Students experimented with small scale paper models to understand the surface and form created by tectonic strategies.

Figure 9. VisCom Experimental lab process IVS. (Mahbub F, 2017)

Day **three** started with fashion lab exercise, where fashion department tutors demonstrated techniques like folding, wrapping, pleating tucking by giving demo on fabric swatches and asked students to experiment with fabric as it was a completely new material for interior design students. After learning the basic construction of tectonic forms, students crafted the shapes into more complex forms and developed understanding of voids,

structural skin, and geometric manipulation of basic forms.

Day four, Begins with the project site in which the students were given design-built brief to construct a live scale installation with all the acquired techniques by using Paper and fabric only. The project site is an inactive connecting corridor on the second floor of the old Indus valley building. It was selected for the project display for following reasons.

To make it active by interactive installation design.

To make the students understand spatial dynamics

How to generate new surfaces by using existing volumes of space.

Students after many conceptual interpretation of the space selected the design of a complex chair module on the concept of wearable furniture and construct the form by using various tectonic strategies. The final installation covered all the surfaces of the space starting from the wall, to the floor and culminating at the ceiling.

The final result of the experimental studio lab ended with the understanding of complex form, structure and surface. Student's feedback was incredibly positive, they felt that they are better equipped in skills, imaginative, cognitive and visual techniques and representation of their design ideas.

After the workshop results it was decided that the next step is to take this workshop on digital medium and to introduce the software modules from second year rather than to start from the advance level studios to equip students with manual and digital skills so that the design process will be better and efficient.

8. Conclusion

Design education should embrace a new paradigm that values creative experience. It not only the need of the time but also the complexity of the nature of design studio that studio methodology also values creative experience for students. It should indulge them in creative thinking and design built projects.

The new era is bringing vast technological advancements, with multiple challenges in the field of design. As the world is getting connected, complexities in design problems are increasing at a rapid scale. Today designers are facing multiple challenges and complex working environments. Similarly discipline of design is living through extraordinary transformations and interdisciplinary design pedagogy is one of the most imperative approaches from which we can create better opportunities and chances of success for future designers.

Figure 10. VisCom Experimental lab product IVS. (Mahbub F, 2017)

9. References

- AMIR, (2001). The design process in Architecture a Pedagogic approach using interactive thinking (PhD). the University of Leeds School of civil engineering United Kingdom.
- Broke, H. Patricia, M. Mark, and Wigley. Embankment galleries (London, Eng.), & museum of contemporary art (Los Angeles, Calif.). (2008). Skin + bones: parallel practices in fashion and architecture, exhibition guidebook, 24 April -10 august, 2008, embankment galleries at Somerset house / [organized by the museum of contemporary art, Los Angeles]. London, Somerset house
- Design's Inherent Interdisciplinary: The Arts in Integrated Curricula Meredith Davis One of three articles for Arts Education Policy Review, Heldref Publications, Washington, DC – Vo. 101, No. 1, September/October 1999
- Erkan, (2013): Interdisciplinary collaboration between Interior architecture and industrial product design.
- Procedia social and Behavioral science; 4th International conference on new horizons in education 106(2013) 154-1547.
- Hadjiyann. T. (2006). Beyond Concepts - A studio pedagogy for preparing tomorrow's designers; .arch.net.<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/5fb1e255148cb1ac58c76c33d891cc9fdff6e89b.pdf>
- Jiangmei Wu (2017): Body, form, material and surface-making of Ruga Interior Skin, Interiors, And DOI: 10.1080/20419112.2017.1374026
- Leila, W, K. (2000). Fashion and Fabrication in Modern Architecture: Goffried Semper, Der Stil in den technischen, (Frankfurt am Main, 1860-1863), Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians, Vol. 58, No. 3, Architectural History, (pp.472-481).University of California press on behalf of the Society of Architectural Historians. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/991541>.
- Lauren, Prasad. B (2014). INTERDISCIPLINARITY IN DESIGN EDUCATION BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES. The Design School, Arizona State University.http://www.idsa.org/sites/default/files/FINAL_Interdisciplinarity%20in%20Design%20Education.pdf.
- Margaret. K. (2011). Build-to-Learn: An Examination of Pedagogical Practices in Interior Design Education, M.F.A., Montana State University <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/joid.12026>
- Mike. T, (2015). Design pedagogy: Developments in Art and design education published by Routledge
- Palencia, P.E.A. (2014), Intersection: Reciprocal influences between similar practices in fashion and architecture (BA thesis in fashion design). <https://skemman.is/bitstream/1946/.../BA%20Final%20Essay%20Andres%20Pelaez.pdf>.
- Palencia, P.E.A. (2014), Intersection: Reciprocal influences between similar practices in fashion and architecture (BA thesis in fashion design). <https://skemman.is/bitstream/1946/.../BA%20Final%20Essay%20Andres%20Pelaez.pdf>
- Podesta, D.M.I. (2013).Influence of Fashion upon Architecture. Is there a relationship between the form and Structure of fashion and architecture (Dissertation) <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKEwj955vut8vaAhXLL48KHco3CJkQFggkMAA&url=https%3A%2F%2Ffolio.brighton.ac.uk%2Fartefact%2Ffile%2Fdownload.php%3Ffile%3D54623%26view%3D14028&usg=AOvVaw1LXFFF9Qh0Ym5tElybhEaJ>.
- Soliman, (2016): Appropriate teaching and learning strategies for the architectural design process in

pedagogic design studios.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foar.2017.03.002>Get rights and content.

10. Images

Eisenman architects, (2015). Max Reinhardt Haus building in Berlin. Retrieved 20 April 2018
www.eisenmanarchitects.com/max-reinhardt.html

J. Meejin Yoon's. (2005). Mobius Dress. Retrieved from 21 April 2018 www.designersparty.com/entry/Mobius-Dress-Meejin-Yoon

Farah J, (2017). VisCom Experimental lab process IVS student work. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/BTx7v83jk1/?hl=en&taken-by=farahmahbub>.

Farah J, (2017). VisCom Experimental lab process IVS student work. Retrieved from <https://www.instagram.com/p/BTqsrAsj4px/?hl=en&taken-by=farahmahbub>.

Frank Gehry, (1999-2003). Walt Disney Concert Hall, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:WaltDisneyConcertHall.jpeg>. Accessed on 21 April 2018. Gareth Pugh, (1966). Shots from William Klein's film Who Are You, Polly Maggoo? (Qui êtes-vous, Polly Maggoo?) From: Palermo, O. (2011) Fashion in Film. <http://oliviapalermo.com/fashion-in-film-%E2%80%AAqui-etes-vous-polly-maggoo%E2%80%AC/>

Herzog & de Meuron. (2003). Prada Store in Tokyo. Retrieved 21 April 2018. www.herzogdemeuron.com/index/projects/complete.../178-prada-aoiyama.html. Yoshiki Hishinuma. (2004). Inside out 2way Dress. Retrieved 19 April 2018. <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/106116134948687835>

Jiangmei Wu, (2017). Body, form, material and surface-making of Ruga Interior Skin. Folded paper model Yoshimura pattern, pg. 8 figure 3 and 4 <https://doi.org/10.1080/20419112.2017.1374026>

Lagerfeld. (2011-2012).Channel couture collection. Retrieved from www.vogue.it/en/shows/show/fw-11-12-haute-couture/chanel

Lagerfeld. (2011-2012).Channel couture collection. Retrieved from www.vogue.it/en/shows/show/fw-11-12-haute-couture/chanel

Leila, W. K. (2000). Fashion and Fabrication in Modern Architecture: Goffried Semper, Der Stil in den technischen, (Frankfurt am Main, 1860-1863), Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians, Vol. 58, No. 3, Architectural History, (pp.472-481).University of

California press on behalf of the Society of Architectural Historians. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/991541>.

Toyo, (2006). Tod's Omotesando building. Retrieved April.2018.<https://thearchiblog.wordpress.com/2011/01/07/toyo-ito-tod-s-omotesando>

Testa &Weiser, (2008). The Carbon Beach House in Los Angeles by Testa & Weiser. From: EMBANKMENT GALLERIES (LONDON, ENG.), & MUSEUM OF CONTEMPORARY ART (LOS ANGELES, CALIF.). (2008). Skin + bones: parallel Practices in fashion and architecture, exhibition guidebook, 24 April - 10 August, 2008, Embankment Galleries at Somerset House / [organized by The Museum of Contemporary Art, Los Angeles]. London, Somerset House